

Letter to Boris Johnson (UK Prime Minister)
30th November 2020
Addendum to paper - 'UK Covid 19 Deaths in the Elderly'

In June this year (2020) I prepared the above paper about the underlying causes behind the large number of deaths in the over 60s age range in the UK due to covid 19 infections. As an addendum to that document there was a mention of the approach which Madagascar had taken in the use of a plant based remedy for the pandemic treatment; the use of artemisia annua tea. The prime minister of Madagascar claimed in April 2020 that this herbal remedy was effective in both curing and preventing a serious illness arising from infection by the covid 19 virus. After this initial claim had been dented by many western countries and the W.H.O. - he made statistical records of the effects of the medication on his population. Hence in May 2020 he further claimed that the tests done on human cases had substantiated his claims for the use of the herbal remedy; and that the evidence he had from tests on human beings was equivalent to the western requirement for clinical trials. It was not described as an ultimate cure but as a support to the human immune system and thereby assisting recovery from the infection.

Let me state one obvious, but often unspoken fact, clinical trials are required for modern synthetic medicines because of the dangers they present to human health. The above mentioned article - "UK covid 19 Deaths ---" makes it clear that modern medicines are the cause of millions of deaths world-wide. See the section "Medicines and the UK NHS" in that article. On the other hand plant based medicines (herbal remedies) have been used, in many cases, on human beings for thousands of years, and in all other cases hundreds of years. These are the equivalent of the modern requirement for clinical trials for synthetic medicines. We should not overlook this important aspect when comparing the two types of medicine. To make a requirement for clinical trials for herbal remedies is out of place in most cases, since the very few plants which can cause problems are already well known and their adverse effects are well documented.

In late April 2020, as a result of the statements by the Prime Minister of Madagascar, the Max Planck institute began to investigate the effects of artemisia annua. It was found in May 2020 that there were significant effects of an artemisia extract using ethanol, on various viruses. In June 2020 the same organisation announced that the same extract had shown positive results of being active against SARS-Cov-2 - the covid 19 pandemic virus. In May 2020 in the USA the university of Kentucky started carrying out clinical trials with artemisia annua in connection with covid-19 patients. So far the claims made by the Prime Minister of Madagascar appear to be substantiated. Yet we must be clear here; the Madagascar claims are for a tea made from the plants leaves. Whereas the western scientific approach is to use extract using ethanol. There does not seem to be a comparison between these two and the chemistry which each contains. It is likely that the tea, if brewed for about 20 minutes, will have more of the plants healing properties than the ethanol extract. Herbalists know that one of the easiest and most effective ways of administering a herbal remedy is to brew a tea from the whole herb.

In November 2020 the England UK was plunged into a second lockdown due to the second wave of covid 19 showing to be worse than the first. It may be that the huge damage to the health and the economy of the UK could have been avoided if the government had looked seriously into the use of the above herbal remedy in April 2020.

Hence it became necessary for me to write to the UK Prime Minister.

The Letter

Dr. Alan Wenham-Prosser DProf., MA.
XX Xxxxxx Road
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30th October 2020

Rt. Honourable Boris Johnson
Prime Minister of the UK
10 Downing Street
London SW 1A 2AA

Dear Mr. Johnson,

I guess it is unlikely that you will get to read this letter, as one of your staff will read it and keep it from you. But the content of it is vital for consideration of the current situation with the covid 19 pandemic as it is now ripping through the nation. I wish you could really get the opportunity to give the nation five minutes of your time to consider it. To ignore it is to continue to condemn many more people to an early grave and many businesses to collapse.

The current problem is not easy for people in high office to either clearly see nor to clearly admit. But it is as clear, as the mountain is to the climber from the plane, to many deeper thinking people in the UK. It is - that those in high office cannot see the easiest way out of the current crisis and do not really know what to do next.

For "people in high office" mentioned above I include the top medical people and the top scientists of this country of ours. But believe it or not, an almost unknown country, part of the African continent, has discovered the way to reduce the cases and deaths of the covid 19 pandemic. But this has been ignored by all those people who are part of the scientific and health communities across the world. Including the W.H.O. This is a serious, and damaging, Western blind-spot. The UK is worse than most in this respect.

I may not be a very important person, and you do not know me, and may wish to take no notice of what I am putting before you. But just to let you know, in 2002, I was appointed by Mr. John Prescott's Deputy Prime Minister's Office to be an Approved Inspector for Building Regulations for 5 years, during which time I was the sole person responsible for passing and inspecting more than 250 projects in the London area. Some of which were prestigious constructions for clients like Goldman Sachs bank and other well to do developers in the City area; totalling many hundreds of millions of £UK. All the projects were completed 100% successfully; legally.

But this letter is not about me. It is about a country with 27 million people which currently has, like everywhere else, the virus all over their land. At the time of writing this letter they have had a total of 608 cases of covid virus per million of population along with 9 deaths per million. Compared to the UK's 14,554 cases per million and the deaths at a staggering 680 per million. Almost the highest in the world. This is unacceptable.

If you do not consider the lower numbers above as a success in dealing with the virus then I would say common sense has deserted every person in high office.

I know the question of numbers is a difficult thing to follow or even in many cases, to believe. For example - who believes that China has had a total of 60 cases per million and 6 deaths per million. But getting the truth out of China is, as you know, like pulling

teeth. In fact getting any true information out of China is nigh impossible. But the country I am writing about is Madagascar. They have as many doubters and reporters who are willing to blow the whistle as any other free country. And even if we multiply their stated numbers by 3 (then 1,824 cases/m & 27 deaths/m) then the UK still has 8 times as many cases and 25 times as many deaths per million; instead of what is officially 24 times the number of cases and 75 times the number of deaths as those in Madagascar.

The reason for their success was stated by their Prime Minister, Andry Rajoelina, in April this year. But because he was using an "untested" remedy the W.H.O. and many others, dismissed the claims he made. After six months of evidence we can no longer ignore what Madagascar has done. But the problem you have and many western nations have, is that they are stuck in the mud of absolute belief in modern scientifically produced synthetic medicines. Which naturally need years of clinical trials because of the dangers they present to the health of people. Plant based medicines have already passed the test.

Madagascar, along with many other countries, have for hundreds of years used natural medicines derived from plants. It is these hundreds of years which replace the few years of clinical trials used for modern medicines. Hence we all need to realise that the W.H.O.'s claim that Madagascar's remedy was not tested is misplaced. And the world's dismissal of the remedy has been responsible for the deaths of too many people and the ruin of so many economies. Madagascar's remedy as proved itself safe for all users.

Madagascar has used an ancient herbal remedy used, ironically, in China for thousands of years. It is called *Artemisia Annua*. It does not do any harm to those who take it. If it did there would be many people reporting such harm from Madagascar, as nearly all the population is taking it. It is not a cure but it has clearly helped all those who have taken it to overcome the illness. Which is the same thing we expect from a vaccine. Any vaccine is not a silver bullet, it only helps the person's own immune system to fight off the virus - if they are lucky. *Artemisia Annua* does the same thing.

You, or your advisors, may already have embraced the subject of alternative medicines; and maybe *Artemisia Annua*. But now is the time to put pride to one side and take a fresh look at *Artemisia Annua*. It will not cost the country £millions (or even £billions which are already spent) and it will not harm anyone. Those who are not prepared to give this a chance to help us all, will become responsible for the damage to businesses and life of all those who will suffer in the next months (or years).

I am 76 years old and have a bottle of *Artemisia Annua* tincture in my medicine cupboard. I have absolute faith that, if needed, it will help me to beat the virus. This virus is a product of Nature. Nature also provides the remedies for all the problems it throws at us. Ancient people knew this. We may think we are wise. But we may have a long way to go to equal those wiser people of times past, who derived cures from Nature.

Please have compassion on the people of this country and give it a chance. If it proves later that this valid remedy was known to you and available cheaply; it may be difficult to live with the responsibility of ignoring it and the cost/devastation caused.

I rest my case. No need to reply. I do not expect any result from this letter.

Dr. Alan Wenham-Prosser DProf., MA. (researcher into all matters of health)

The Current Situation

The table below is self explanatory in respect of the current statistics (12/11/2020) for various countries compared to the UK. All those on the table, other than the UK and Madagascar, had shown interest in the Madagascar claim for artemisia annua in April this year; and had placed orders for the purchase of the remedy from Madagascar. However, since the W.H.O. and other eminent scientists and medical people had down-played the Madagascar remedy, most of those countries have kept quiet about what they are doing to help their populations deal with covid 19 infections. The results after more than six months of the pandemic are self explanatory. These results are on millions of covid 19 patients; not the few thousand people; which is the number used for modern clinical trials.

Some people have said that the low incidence of deaths in African countries is due to their high proportion of younger people in their populations. But my original concern was for the effect on the elderly within the UK. Hence I have also shown the proportion of each population where over 60s are concerned. This shows that the use of artemisia annua has still provided a huge benefit to those countries which may have used it.

Country	Total cases	Total deaths	Deaths per million	Population	Proportion age over 60
UK	1,290,195	50,928	749	68,017,319	15%
Congo	5,379	92	17	5,566,982	3.7%
Madagascar	17,223	249	9	27,946,942	4%
Togo	2,605	60	7	8,348,674	4.2%
Chad	1,578	100	6	16,594,682	3.9%
Equatorial Guinea	5,104	85	60	1,419,407	4.5%
Tanzania	509	21	0.3	60,343,778	3.6%

If we take into account the proportion of the population over 60 in the UK compared to a country like Madagascar then the factor of deaths per million is still 21 times the number of deaths per million of population. Hence it remains clear that the initial claims made by the Prime Minister of Madagascar should have been taken more seriously. Instead the world listened to the advice from the W.H.O. who made such spurious statements that reliance on untested remedies could damage the nation; in that -- people may not be so keen to take precautions about catching the virus.

Let's unpick this statement. All nations are hoping for a vaccination against covid 19. This remedy, if effective, will allow whole nations to return to normal. But 'normal' means that the population need no longer take precautions against contracting the virus. This is same as the effect of relying on artemisia annua when it was known by the Madagascans that it was effective against covid 19. So what was the value in the statement made by W.H.O. Clearly whoever made that statement did not think it through.

Also we should note here that artemisia annua does more than a vaccine can do. If a person gets a serious illness from covid 19 there is no value in giving that person a vaccine. Artemisia annua also helps an infected person to fight the infection.

I rest my case. - Dr. A.W.P.